

Elaboration and investigation about the mechanical properties of reinforced aligned multi-walled carbon nanotube carpets composites

J. Bouillonec^{1,2,3*}, M. Pinault², G. Bernhart³, M. Mayne-L'Hermite², P. Olivier³, M. Gardou¹
¹CEA, DAM, GRAMAT, F- 46500 Gramat, France

²Laboratoire Francis Perrin (CEA-CNRS URA 2453), CEA Saclay, DSM, IRAMIS, SPAM, 91191 Gif-sur-Yvette, France

³ICA (Institut Clément Ader), UPS (Université de Toulouse), Mines Albi, 81013 Albi, France

* Corresponding author (jonathan.bouillonec@cea.fr)

Keywords: carbon nanotube - multi-walled - alignment - nanocomposite - impregnation process - mechanical properties

1. General Introduction

Carbon nanotubes are very promising materials thanks to their high aspect ratio, specific area, lightness and their outstanding mechanical, thermal and electrical properties at the nanometer scale. Among them **vertically aligned carbon nanotubes (VACNTs)** are very interesting candidates as reinforcement for multifunctional composite materials. 1D oriented-nanocomposites resulting from an impregnation of **VACNTs carpets** with an organic matrix, above all epoxy grades, are particularly interesting because they would bring both an important mechanical stiffness of the polymeric matrix [1], [2] and a significant improvement of the thermal conduction [3], [4] according to several recent papers. Moreover, anisotropic measured properties would be clearly higher than those reached with randomly dispersed CNTs filled composites. However until now, very few studies have been carried out about the development of such materials at a macroscopic scale and the study of the effect of these linked and oriented nanotubes on the final properties of these ones. This paper is going to try to answer some of these issues.

2. Context, issue and approach

For twenty years and the official discovery of the existence of the structure of carbon nanotubes [5] (CNTs), many studies have shown their outstanding properties (mechanical, electrical, thermal): for one individual nanotube, a Young's modulus higher than 1.0 TPa [6], [7,] [8], a thermal conductivity going over one thousand W/m.K [9], an electrical conductivity equal to those of semiconductors... This is the reason why an intense

research has notably been carried out with the aim to incorporate them within different matrixes both as **reinforcement of nanocomposites** [10] and also more recently as **conductor channels** (of heat and current) [11], [12]. Contrary to most of the studies reported in the litterature on this kind of nanocomposite until now, our approach is clearly different because it doesn't deal neither with randomly dispersed CNTs within a matrix, nor with aligned ones in the plan, but with vertically aligned CNTs arranged as a carpet (perpendicularly to the plan of the prepared composite). Thus an improvement of mechanical and thermal properties in certain directions can be expected thanks to the anisotropy of these latest. Therefore, aeronautic and astronautic fields are particularly targeted by this study whose ambition would be to achieve the following compromise between:

- a lightening in the weight of structures (in order to save fuel and to increase the embedded load),
- a capacity to better dissipate the heat generated by electronic systems (by amplifying the thermal diffusivity and conductivity of some parts),
- a structural reinforcement as equivalent as current composite materials', particularly in some privileged directions

From this foreword, the purpose of this work is the elaboration of **reinforced aligned multi-walled carbon nanotube (AMWCNTs) carpets composites** and the assessment of some of their **mechanical properties**.

We will mainly focus on the effect of the main characteristics forming the CNTs carpet

(length, mean external diameter, surface density in CNTs) and also on the impregnation techniques used on the mechanical properties of these 1D-nanocomposites (in both longitudinal and transverse directions compared with the main axis of the CNTs).

The approach will consist in three main consecutive steps:

i) The aerosol-assisted chemical vapour deposition (CVD) synthesis of **MWCNTs arranged in the form of carpets** (so oriented in one preferential direction) owing **some tailored inner characteristics** (length, mean external diameter, surface density in CNTs, crystalline structure, aspect ratio, relative density, CNTs volume fraction),

ii) Both the development and the upscaling of **many impregnation methods** of these aligned MWCNTs carpets by different organic epoxy resins in order to **elaborate 1D-oriented nanocomposites**,

iii) The measurement and estimation of **some mechanical properties** (elastic modulus, ultimate tensile stress and strain, hardness...) for these anisotropic composites

The research work aims to take advantage of the alignment of multi-walled CNT carpets (synthesized with a liquid-aerosol CVD technique) within different kinds of organic matrixes in order to improve the mechanical properties of the only matrix. At the end, we would wish identify the most promising applications according to the respective group of material and their characteristics.

Very few teams have already investigated a thorough study about the properties of this kind of 1D-nanocomposite: to our knowledge, Brian Wardle's group at the « Aeronautic & Astronautics Department » of MIT is undoubtedly the one who went the furthest by achieving some indentation and compression on aligned MWCNTs reinforced mini-pillar composites (with an increasing of some GPa and MPa for the modulus and the hardness respectively [1], [13], [14]) and also some measurements of thermal conductivity which rises up from 0.26 for the matrix to about 5.0 W/m.K for the nanocomposite in the parallel direction compared with the main axis of the CNTs [3].

3. Synthesis of vertically aligned MWCNTs carpets

Many methods have been discovered and optimized in order to synthesize vertically aligned mono and multi-walled CNTs carpets with different tailored characteristics. Among all of them, Catalytic Chemical Vapor Deposition techniques (CCVD) consisting in **continuously** feeding a reactor with **liquid precursors** (containing both a carbonaceous source and a catalytic precursor) are flexible (continuous growth of VACNTs carpets **in one step**), economically viable (production of CNTs in high quantity on large reaction surface substrates, with high growth rates) and energetically interesting (« mean » temperature required between 500 and 1 100 °C).

Compared with most of other CVD liquid processes (notably the ones with pre-deposition of the catalyst), it has many interests: the handling is quite easy, the saving in time is significant and it doesn't induce a saturation of the catalyst in carbon which would be likely to decrease the growth rate. Moreover it provides a reliable control on the main characteristics of MWCNTs such as length, external diameter, surfacic density, relative density, the mean alignment degree and the cleanness of the central core.

This aerosol-assisted CVD method [15], [16], [17] consists in injecting **continuously and simultaneously** a solution made of both a carbon (toluene) and a catalytic precursor (ferrocene) inside a synthesis reactor as micro-droplets similar to a spray (see the diagram *Fig. 1*). These latest ones are careered with an argon flow, vaporized in an evaporator (at 200 °C) and then pyrolysed in a quartz reactor heated by a furnace at 800-850 °C. Ferrocene (mass rate of 2.5 % diluted into toluene) thermally decomposes itself in gaseous phase, iron-based catalytic nanoparticles settle on the internal surface of a quartz reactor (and also on growth substrates beforehand put in this latest), then the catalytic decomposition of toluene happens from these ones and finally we have a germination and the initiation of the vertically aligned MWCNTs growth according to a base-growth mechanism [17]. Thus we quickly get (high growth rates of 30-60 $\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) an aligned MWCNTs carpet with a good alignment degree compared with the normal to the substrate.

All synthesized CNTs are aligned in a privileged direction (**perpendicularly to the growth substrate**) and linked between one another (thanks to Van der Waals bonds) in the form of a carpet able to reach a few millimeter-long in thickness (see Fig. 2a), 2b), 2c)).

Our approach includes many original features compared with all the studies reported in the literature until now: contrary to most of works dealing with the elaboration, the characterization and the estimation of properties of randomly oriented (dispersed) CNTs reinforced nanocomposites, CNTs manufactured here are **all aligned in one direction and interdependent** by forming a few millimeter-long carpet (see below Fig. 2a, 2b and 2c).

We can indeed quite easily vary some experimental conditions (nature and concentration of the catalytic precursor, nature and flow of the carrier gas, duration of the injection, synthesis temperature, post-annealing...) in order to tailor the characteristics of the VACNT carpets.

VACNTs carpets obtained own thicknesses which increase with the synthesis duration, they have a narrow diameter distribution (mean internal and external diameter respectively centered around 8 ± 3 nm, and 50 ± 15 nm / 25 ± 15 nm depending on the synthesis conditions which are imposed), they are systematically multi-walled [17], they have very few by-products (iron mass rate below 4-5 %, equal to zero in case of annealing under pure argon at 2 000 °C, see Fig. 3a)) which are mostly located inside the CNTs, and they are dense in surface (from 2.0 to $4.0 \cdot 10^9$ NTCs/cm²). Independently from the variation in length of the CNTs (from 100 μm to several mm), two distinct families of aligned CNT carpets have been prepared thanks to the choice of two different synthesis atmospheres (see Fig. 3b-3c and 3d-3e): the first one with a mean external diameter of 25 nm (called **VACNT-25**) and the other one with a mean external diameter of 50 nm (named **VACNT-50**). Both of them have a mean intertube free space of about 100 nm.

The graphs of the distribution in external diameter have been obtained owing to a statistic study of many TEM pictures. Complementary analysis with TEM observations demonstrates the presence of the iron-based catalytic residue inside the core of MWCNTs (see Fig. 4). Indeed TGA (thermogravimetric analysis) under air brought out mass valued lower than 2.0-2.5 wt % after a clear pyrolysis of the CNT carpet from about 550 to 700 °C (see Fig. 5).

4. Impregnation methods of vertically aligned MWCNT carpets and elaboration of 1 D-oriented nanocomposite

Two impregnation techniques have been chosen to impregnate the VACNT-25 and VACNT-50 dry carpets:

- a **liquid immersion way** with the epoxy system **EPON 812** (supplier Sigma-Aldrich). It consists in blending in imposed proportions a resin, a hardener and an accelerator, in outgasing this mixture before and after an impregnation of the CNT carpet that is immersed within a teflon mold, and then in curing it (60°C during 3-4 days) in order to polymerize the organic matrix at atmospheric pressure,
- an **infusion process**, very common on large structure parts in aeronautic field, whose principle is to carry along a liquid resin by depression (thanks to a vacuum pump). The continuous flow enables to impregnate the reinforcement (the MWCNT carpets in our case) put on a heating table thanks to a draining grid disposed above and a high-vacuum tarpaulin with its mastic which makes the vacuum possible.

This second process has been implemented at the Institut Clément Ader (ICA Albi) on two structural epoxy resins, developed for infusion and RTM techniques:

- the **SICOMIN system** resulting from a blend between a resin (SR 1710 Injection) and its hardener (SD 8822) in determined proportions (see Fig. 6a), injection at room

temperature, curing during 16h00 at 60 °C under vacuum ;

- the monocomponent premixed **Hexflow® RTM 6** system (made by Hexcel Composite) is preheated until 80 °C and then infused at 120 °C (see *Fig. 6b*). After the complete impregnation of the aligned MWCNT carpets, a curing process at 180 °C during 2h00 under vacuum is necessary to achieve the manufacturing of the composite.

The three epoxy grades are disposed together in the form of pellets on *Fig. 7*.

Except the corners of the MWCNT carpets which are slightly crushed by the vacuum bag, we see no loss of shape both visually and at the SEM even at low carbon nanotube volume fractions.

For these two processes after the demolding, a delicate polishing and machining (with a diamond wire saw) step finally (see *Fig. 8*) enables to achieve a few millimeters-thick and mirror-polished composite (on both faces).

Many FEG-SEM observations (see *Fig. 9a-f*) on both faces and in the cross-section (after a nitrogen cryofracturation) of the nanocomposite show a good impregnation state and no porosity or voids at the micro-scale despite a mean close inter-tube space about 100 nm.

A gangue of resin surrounding each carbon nanotube (see *Fig. 9f*) is clearly visible, which proves a good affinity in term of wetting between the three epoxy systems and the MWCNTs.

For these two kinds of MWCNT carpets (VACNT-25 and 50) reinforcing the organic matrix, some measurements by hydrostatic weight (in air and immersed in isopropanol) and also confirmed more accurately by helium pycnometry conducted ranges of relative density values reported in the *diagram 1*.

As we know the relative density values of both polymerized epoxy systems and nanocomposites (hydrostatic weight into water), and also the value of the MWCNT carpet (raw and dry before impregnation), we can access CNT volume fractions thanks to the following theoretical law of

mixture:

$$d_{\text{Nanocomposite}} = d_{\text{MWCNTs carpet}} * \psi_{\text{Volum. MWCNTs}} + d_{\text{Epoxy}} * (1 - \psi_{\text{Volum. MWCNTs}}) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

With: $d_{\text{Nanocomposite}}$, $d_{\text{MWCNTs carpet}}$ and d_{Epoxy} the respective relative density for the nanocomposite, the MWCNTs carpet and the epoxy system
 $\psi_{\text{Volum. NTCs}}$ the volume fraction in MWCNTs (%)

This formula ideally supposes there is no porosity inside the material, a perfect wetting between each carbon nanotube and the epoxy resin, and also an alignment degree equal to zero. The diagram called "*Tab. 1*" sums up the measured and calculated values at the bottom of this paper.

A characterization carried out on small nanocomposite composite samples on a X-microtomograph (CEA Gramat) with a minimal pixel size resolution image of 460 nm showed absolutely no irregularity or porosity at this scale. It seems to demonstrate a perfect impregnation of each nanotube, even if we would like to decrease lower in resolution to probe the nanotube-organic resin interface.

A chemical degradation technique with sulfuric acid and the addition of hydrogen peroxide (EN NF 2564 French aeronautic norm dedicated to laminate carbon fiber fabric) has also been another reliable and complementary method employed in order to check the CNT volume fraction values.

After the matrix has been destroyed and the remaining material has been clean, dried and weighted, we get a practically similar value (12.09 %) to the one obtained with the first technique (10.93 %) by using (*Eq. 1*). This is confirmed with SEM observations where we notice that all the nanotubes homogeneously remained aligned in the shape of a carpet (see *Fig. 10*), and that above all the whole matrix vanished.

5. Mechanical traction tests (transverse direction % MWCNTs) on epoxy and nanocomposite « aligned MWCNTs carpet / epoxy »

Some mechanical tension tests have been carried out on mini-beams (machined with a diamond wire saw) of polymerized epoxy systems and aligned VACNTs carpets / epoxy nanocomposites (14 mm gage length with a section of $2.0 * 2.0 \text{ mm}^2$, see *Fig. 11a*). A stress-strain device dedicated to mini-traction (INSTRON 5942) with manual tightening jaws and a strength force of 500 Newtons has been used. Composites are stretched in the transverse direction regarding the main alignment axis of the nanotubes (see *Fig. 11b*).

In order to only consider the contribution of the deformation of the mini-pillars, and as we can't implement an extensometer on them (cause of the small size of the samples), two strategies have been adopted:

- a) Locally measuring the real strain thanks to a small strain gage stuck at the middle of the beam coupled to a dynamic data acquisition system (Vishay);
- b) Using the digital image correlation (DIC) technique in monovision thanks to a camera which takes pictures of the strained material during the traction coupled with a dedicated software (Vic-2D). A texture called speckle has to be coated all along the beam in order to be able to follow the local displacement of pixels containing some of these painting droplets (size meshing between 25 and 45 with a step of 5). There is no contact to achieve it and the mean displacement is probed on the whole length of the sample.

The chart “*Tab. 2*” gives the main results got for the Young's modulus and the ultimate tensile strain according to both methods.

We notice the Young's modulus for the nanocomposite (with CNTs volume fractions of 3.9 and 14 %) is slightly higher than the resin's, whereas the rupture strain decreases. Indeed the material becomes both stiffer (thanks to the creation of billions of CNT-epoxy nanobonds) and more fragile (many interfaces created) when we incorporate

carbon nanotubes within an epoxy matrix. Both methods give quite close results, even if the DIC is much more reliable because it induces a local acquisition of the strain all along the sample and also for the strain gage (directly in contact with the beam) is likely to stiffen this one and to generate some deviations compared with the real strain of the composite. An estimation based on the ideal law of mixture supposing a perfect alignment of the CNTs and an optimal wetting of these latest by the resin (see *Eq. 1*) enables finally to access a **radial** (or **transverse**) Young's modulus value higher than 10 GPa for the carpet, so for each carbon nanotube. Finally the incorporation of CNTs seems to increase the Poisson's ratio from 0.35-0.38 to values higher than 0.40 (this trend has to be confirmed).

6. Surfacic nanoindentation tests on epoxy matrix and « aMWCNTs array / epoxy » nanocomposites (transverse and longitudinal direction)

Nanoindentation tests performed on (perfectly plane and mirror-polished) epoxy resin and « VACNT carpet / epoxy » nanocomposites samples (in both transverse and longitudinal directions of anisotropy compared with the main alignment axis of the CNTs) have also been carried out and compared (see *fig. 12 and 12b*). The nanoindenter (CSM Instrument, ISAE-ENSICA Toulouse) used here consists in measuring the applied load on a material by a very stiff diamond pyramidal tip called Berkovich gradually with the penetration depth of this one over a thickness of $1.0 \mu\text{m}$.

For each indentation, we get a load-unload curve (see *Fig. 13*) which enables to calculate (via a theory called Oliver & Pharr) two essential mechanical parameters which are representative of the surface of any material: the **elastic modulus** and the **hardness**.

The first one is calculated from the slope “S” of the unload curve by assuming that the Poisson's ratio of the resin and the nanocomposite is 0.30, and the second one by dividing the maximum load by the contact area with the indent.

The tables *Tab. 2a, 2b and 2c* got for the epoxy system EPON 812 alone and the “VACNT

carpet / EPON 812” nanocomposite sum up the trends systematically observed for the three families of elaborated nanocomposite materials (with EPON 812, SICOMIN and RTM 6).

As a result from many indentations on the three kinds of composites already described, the increasing in modulus and hardness values are quite significant from the indentation on the surface of a polymerized epoxy system to CNTs reinforced composite in the TRANSVERSE orientation, which is itself highly mechanically reinforced when we indent in the PARALLEL direction to the main axis of the CNTs (modulus multiplied by 2.5 and hardness by 3 compared with the organic matrix).

The (Eq. 1) applied to the elastic modulus also leads to calculate theoretical values of this parameter for aligned VACNT carpets in these two anisotrope directions. We reach a maximum value of about **42** and **60 GPa** in the longitudinal direction for both composite “VACNT-25 / EPON 812” and “VACNT-50 / EPON 812” respectively, which is at least one order of magnitude below the (both theoretically and experimentally) reported value for individual carbon nanotube in the literature (about 1,0 Terapascal).

In the perpendicular and above all parallel direction to the main axis of CNTs, the graphs of *Fig. 14a and 14b* clearly exhibit the higher the CNT volume fraction, the higher the mechanical parameters values. This is a major result demonstrating the reinforcement role provided by the CNTs. However the effect of the CNT length, their aspect ratio and crystalline quality is not enough explicit to be able to demonstrate other trends for instance.

To come back the literature already quoted [1], [13], [14], this is awkward to compare these data to ours because the synthesis technique, the characteristics of the MWCNTs and the mechanical method used to vary the CNT volume fraction considerably differs from ours and induce major differences as a result. In parallel, few other authors such as Musso-Dassios [2] can synthesize VACNT carpets with an absolutely similar technique to ours (and close regarding the characteristics of MWCNTs), but they especially stress on physico-

chemical properties without going until to test the mechanical behavior of the nanocomposites reinforced by these carpets.

Conclusion and outlook

Different impregnation methods and physico-chemical characterization techniques aiming both to elaborate VACNT carpets/epoxy composite with different and tailored characteristics have been implemented. Tension and nanoindentation tests notably exhibited a relatively consistent improvement in stiffness and hardness with the incorporation of aligned MWCNTs within an epoxy polymerized system.

As an outlook, further characterisations are in progress or upcoming (wetting tests with model solvents and the epoxy resin employed, X-tomography, measurement of thermal diffusivity according to different methods, study of the effect of some reactive ion etching treatments on the surface of composite samples), and mechanical tests (notably compression ones) have to be continued to confirm the trends, make the results more reliable and of course understand the phenomena happening at the nanometric scale. Finally a work about the optimization of the methods dedicated to the elaboration of the VACNT carpets reinforced composites will be carry out, notably for the upscaling of the materials (30 * 120 mm, A4)

Acknowledgment

- Midi-Pyrénées region for the funding of the ARCON project (Amélioration de la conduction thermique de composites pour applications spatiales par ARchitecture organisée de « canaux CONducteurs » dans l'épaisseur du matériau) and the co-funding of the thesis
- Ile-de-France region for the purchase of the FEG-SEM of the SPAM (CEA Saclay)
- M. Paternostre, TEM platform of CEA-DSV (CEA-Saclay)
- T. Martin, tests on the nanoindentator (ISAE-ENSICA Toulouse)
- P. Rey and A. Fanget (CEA Gramat) for the analysis by X-microtomography

References

- morphology », *Composites Science & Technology* 69, 2649-2656, **2009**
- [15] M. Pinault et al., « Growth of multiwalled carbon nanotubes during the initial stages of aerosol-assisted CCVD », *Carbon* 43, 2968–2976, **2005**.
- [16] M. Pinault et al., « Evidence of Sequential Lift in Growth of Aligned Multiwalled Carbon Nanotube Multilayers », *Nano Letters*, Vol. 5, N° 12, **2005**.
- [17] C. Castro et al., « Dynamics of catalyst particles formation and multi-walled carbon nanotube growth in aerosol-assisted catalytic chemical vapor deposition », *Carbon* 48, p. 3807-3816, **2010**.
- [1] *Thesis* Enrique J. Garcia, « Characterization of composites with aligned carbon nanotube CNTs as reinforcement », University of Saragossa, MIT Department of Aeronautics & Astronautics (B. Wardle's group), **2006**.
- [2] K.G. Dassios et al., « Compressive behaviour of MWCNT/epoxy composite mats », *Composite Science & Technology* 72, p. 1027-1033, **2012**.
- [3] *Thesis* Namiko Yamamoto, « Multi-scale electrical and thermal properties of aligned multi-walled carbon nanotubes and their composites », MIT Department of Aeronautics & Astronautics (B. Wardle's group), **2010**.
- [4] Q. Gong et al. – « Thermal properties of aligned carbon nanotube/carbon nanocomposites » – *Materials Science and Engineering A* 384 – p. 209-214, **2004**.
- [5] Ijima, « Helical microtubules of graphitic carbon », *Nature*, vol. 354, **1991**
- [6] Yu et al., « Strength and breaking mechanism of multi-walled carbon nanotubes under tensile load », *Science*, n°5453, 637-640, **2000**
- [7] Salvetat et al., Mechanical properties of carbon nanotube, *Appl. Phys. A* 69, 255-260, **1999**
- [8] Demczyk et al., « Direct mechanical measurement of the tensile strength and elastic modulus of multiwalled carbon nanotubes », *Materials Science and Engineering A*, 173-178, **2002**
- [9] Kim et al., « Thermal Transport Measurements of Individual Multiwalled Nanotubes », *Physical Review Letters*, Vol. 87, n°21, **2001**
- [10] Ajayan et al., « Aligned carbon nanotube arrays formed by cutting a polymer resin-nanotube composite », *Science*, vol. 265, **1994**
- [11] Patent application of H. Le Khanh et al. (filed by Thalès company), WO2012/126955A1
- [12] Lin et al., « Parametric study of intrinsic thermal transport in vertically aligned MWCNTs using a laser flash technique », *Carbon* 50, 1591-1603, **2012**
- [13] Garcia et al., « Fabrication and multifunctional properties of high volume fraction carbon nanotube thermoset composites », *Journal of Nano Systems & Technology*, vol. 1, n°1, October **2009**
- [14] Cebeci et al., « Multifunctional properties of high volume fraction aligned carbon nanotubes polymer nanocomposite with controlled

Fig. 1: Simplified diagram of the aerosol-assisted CVD device enabling to synthesize the **vertically aligned MWCNT carpets**

Fig. 2a: Several aligned MWCNTs carpets after synthesis on their quartz substrate

Fig. 2b: FEG-SEM picture of an aligned MWCNTs carpet at low magnification still dependent on its quartz substrate on which the growth happened (thickness = 1.74 mm)

Fig. 2c: cross-section FEG-SEM picture of an aligned MWCNTs carpet at high magnification (x 20 000)

Fig. 3a: Transmission Electronic Microscope (TEM) picture of clean MWCNTs

Fig. 4: TEM picture showing some catalytic residue

Fig. 3b and 3c: cross-section FEG-SEM picture of VACNT-25 (synthesis of 3 hours at 800 °C under H₂ (30 %) / Ar (70 %) and its external diameter distribution

Fig. 5: TGA curves under air at 1 000 °C on several MWCNTs carpets at 10°C/min

Fig. 3d and 3e: cross-section FEG-SEM picture of VACNT-50 (synthesis of 2 hours at 850 °C under pure Ar (100 %) and its external diameter distribution

Fig. 6a and 6b: infusion method applied to some squared-shape aligned MWCNT carpets (15 * 15 mm * 2.0-3.0 mm thick)

Fig. 7 (from left to right): EPON 812, SR 1710 Injection and RTM 6 epoxy systems pellets

Fig. 8: visual chronology of the successive steps achieving the elaboration of a mirror-polished “VACNT carpet / epoxy” nanocomposite

Fig. 9a, 9b and 9c: Top-view FEG-SEM pictures in TLD mode (« True Length Detector » = high-resolution secondary electrons detector) of mirror-polished reinforced VACNT-50 carpets composite faces (Ø mean

external diameter = 50 nm)

Fig. 9d, 9e and 9f: Side-view FEG-SEM pictures in TLD mode (« True Length Detector » = high-resolution secondary electrons detector) of mirror-polished reinforced VACNT-50 carpets composite sections (\varnothing Mean external diameter = 50 nm)

Material	Density	CNT volume fraction range for the VACNT carpet reinforced composite (%) _ Eq. (1)
VACNT-25 carpet	1.89 – 1.93	1.4 – 4.7
VACNT-50 carpet	1.98 – 2.04	10.9 – 14.8
EPON 812 system	1.297 ± 0.004	
SICOMIN system	1.146 ± 0.001	
RTM 6 system	1.138 ± 0.0001	

Tab. 1 : measured relative density values for the employed VACNT carpets and epoxy systems + CNTs volume fraction ranges for the nanocomposite with matrix EPON 812 / SICOMIN and RTM 6

Fig. 10: FEG-SEM picture of a nanocomposite after a chemical degradation

Fig. 11a: VACNT carpet reinforced composite stuck to

stainless steel heels stretched in tension

Fig. 11b: diagram of the transverse orientation compared with the main axis of the carbon nanotubes

	Material	Young's modulus (GPa)	Ultimate tensile strain (%)
Strain gage	EPON 812 system	3.91	0.71
	Composite « VACNT carpet-EPON 812 » ($\psi_{\text{Volum. CNTs}} = 14,2\%$)	5.93	0.54
	Raw VACNT carpet (calculation with the law of mixtures) - $\psi_{\text{Volum. CNTs}} = 14,2\%$	18.10	\emptyset
Digital image correlation (DIC)	EPON 812 system	3.28 ± 0.06	1.28 ± 0.019
	SICOMIN system	3.53 (TDS:3.68)	2.58 (TDS:3.1)
	RTM 6 system	2.88 (TDS:2.89)	3.71 (TDS:3.4)
	Composite « VACNT carpet-EPON 812 » ($\psi_{\text{Volum. CNTs}} = 3.9\%$)	3.57 ± 0.09	0.91
	Raw VACNT carpet (calculation with the law of mixtures) - $\psi_{\text{Volum. CNTs}} = 14,2\%$	10.59	\emptyset
	Composite « VACNT carpet-EPON 812 » ($\psi_{\text{Volum. CNTs}} = 14.2\%$)	4.48 ± 0.19	$0.78 \pm 0,03$
	Raw VACNT carpet (calculation with the law of mixtures) - $\psi_{\text{Volum. CNTs}} = 14,2\%$	11.72	\emptyset

Fig. 12a and 12b: longitudinal and transverse indentation diagram compared with the orientation of the main axis of the carbon nanotubes

Tab. 2: Mechanical parameters of tension tests on similar epoxy system and aligned MWCNTs carpet reinforced nanocomposite mini-beams

Fig. 13: load-unload curve got after an indentation on any material

EPON 812 epoxy system (after reticulation) (ψ Volum. CNTs = 0 %)	
Modulus EIT (GPa)	5.17
Hardness HIT (MPa)	177.3
Number of indentations	23

Composite "VACNT-50 carpet - EPON 812" (ψ Volum. CNTs = 3.9 %)		
	// % CNTs	⊥ % CNTs
Modulus EIT (GPa)	6.60	5.68
Hardness HIT (MPa)	262.8	205.8
Number of indentations	18	11
Theoretical modulus for the VACNT carpet (GPa)	41.84	18.25

Composite "VACNT-50 carpet - EPON 812" (ψ Volum. CNTs = 14.1 %)		
	// % CNTs	⊥ % CNTs
Modulus EIT (GPa)	12.92	6.35
Hardness HIT (MPa)	675.2	295.1
Number of indentations	55	15
Theoretical modulus for the VACNT carpet (GPa)	60.02	13.52

Tab. 2a, 2b and 2c: Elastic modulus and hardness values for the EPON 812 system alone and its associated nanocomposite + a theoretical value of the MWCNTs carpet's Young's modulus based on the ideal law of mixture (in the transverse and longitudinal direction) for different CNTs volume fractions

Fig. 14a and 14b: Hardness and elastic modulus values versus the CNT volume fraction (VACNT carpet / EPON 812 system nanocomposite) in both transverse and longitudinal directions compared with the main axis of the CNTs